

Deep learning applied to automated visual defect detection for wind towers painting process

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Abstract. Zero Defect Manufacturing (ZDM) strategies focus on promptly and precisely detecting defects to reduce material and energy consumption, and avoid product failure while the product is in use. Integrating a computer vision defect detection system is an important approach to improving the quality of inspection policies and the performance of the manufacturing process. Last year's high attention has been paid to surface image defect detection based on deep learning algorithms. The deep learning methods on automated vision systems require large quantities of annotated data. Acquiring defects is a costly and time-consuming task in industrial contexts since defects only occur in small percentages, data is biased through the predomination of non-defective samples, and there is a lack of publicly available datasets to train the algorithms. This study aims to evaluate the performance of a deep learning algorithm based on the dataset employed and the training parameters selected.

Keywords: Defect detection, artificial intelligence, computer vision, quality inspection, deep learning, surface defects.

1 Introduction

Non-destructive inspection technologies (NDIT) are evolving quickly due to the introduction of new sensors, machine learning algorithms, big data, and the Internet of Things (IoT) [1], [2], [3]. The zero defects manufacturing strategy is a data and technology-driven paradigm that reduces waste and cost and increases product quality and process productivity [4]. To deploy real-time NDIT on the manufacturing shop floor, the solutions should integrate new artificial intelligence technologies to improve the accuracy and automation needs for production implementation [5]. The NDITs are

focused on the execution of repetitive inspection tasks that conventionally are performed out of the line manually or even with destructive methods.

In the painting and coating industrial processes, defects such as pits, holes, underfill, and scratches appear due to failures related to equipment, raw materials or production environment conditions [6]. The painting of wind towers acts as a surface treatment to increase the corrosion resistance of the steel; in the long term, this corrosion mechanism can result in equipment failure due to the high demand conditions of the offshore environment. The painting defects increase the costs incurred by the manufacturers, including reprocessing, warranty, and reputation costs, and reduce the product's service life.

Manual visual inspection is the conventional technique for detecting defects in painting or coating treatments [7]. The painting process quality can be improved if the visual inspection is performed by an automated vision system rather than manually by operators. The performance of automatic vision systems is influenced by the robustness, accuracy and time efficiency in the defect detection process; this article covers these topics and provides an early use case for painting inspection solutions.

Integrating non-destructive inspection solutions based on deep learning algorithms will improve production quality, which can be considered a core competency that industrial companies should possess to improve their performance [8]. Automatic vision inspection systems significantly improve the accuracy and reliability of defect detection since the inspection does not rely on aspects such as operator training, mental or physical fatigue [9], [10].

In recent years, industrial production in various fields (electronic production, steel manufacturing, etc.) has benefited from applying deep learning artificial intelligence algorithms [11]. One of the main advantages that position the deep learning algorithm as a standard in supervised computer vision is that it automatically learns and extracts features with strong predictive value, reducing the preprocessing and fine-tuning required. Deep learning can be considered a subfield of machine learning and artificial intelligence, which, in the last decade, has been demonstrating outstanding performance in defect detection in computer vision [12], [13], [14].

The most common methodology to train deep learning algorithms relies on supervised machine learning [6]. The approach employs the human annotation of the images for classification and object detection for training. Frequently, in industrial environments the main defect samples found in painting or surface defects are assigned to a few types of defects or category, and in the general dataset the vast majority of the data accounts for non-defective samples [5], [15]. The lack of balanced data on deep learning algorithms can produce inaccurate results due to prioritisation performed by the standard loss functions [16]. Therefore, to deploy automatic deep learning visual inspection solutions in industrial product quality detection, a vast amount of data should be acquired, labelled and trained, increasing the algorithm's human labour and computational burden. The main challenge to applying this technology is that defect rates are low in

manufacturing environments, increasing the efforts to obtain a representative dataset since the companies do not offer public dataset [17], [18].

The current author's research objectives are constructing a novel dataset of painting defects and performing several training scenarios to investigate the evolution of the average precision based on the deep learning model employed and the size of the dataset employed.

2 Research Methodology

The deployment of an automatic vision system involves several steps, image acquisition (hardware), image processing, and machine learning, to close the quality assurance loop (Fig. 1). These new Zero Defects Zero Waste (ZDZW) solutions for quality assurance involve various sensors or technologies to create the inspection platform for the final integration with the manufacturing control system.

The accuracy, efficiency and performance of the machine vision-based visual detection equipment not only rely on the artificial intelligence algorithms, but another important parameter is the image acquisition hardware. The conventional computer vision inspection system comprises three modules: image acquisition, image processing, and machine learning (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Automatic vision system diagram for painting inspection.

2.1 Image acquisition hardware

The sensor size and resolution, speed and image stabilization are factors that influence the machine-vision inspection process to detect small defects that occur in the painting process. The camera Basler acA5472-5gc has been selected for the image acquisition system, which uses the Sony IMX183 color CMOS sensor of 20 Megapixels, pixel size $2.4 \times 2.4 \mu\text{m}$ and sensor size of $13.13 \times 8.76 \text{ mm}$. Another basic hardware element for image acquisition is the optical lens, which influences the contrast, aberration, working distance, focal length and field of view. A focal length lens Fujinon Lens CF25ZA-1S F1.8 f25mm 4/3, which provides for a field of view (FOV) of around 30 cm in width and 20 cm in height (around 18 px/mm of spatial resolution), is employed. The selected camera and lens allow the acquisition of images from the wind tower for defect detection with a working distance of around 50-55 cm. Strategically mounting up to six cameras on an autonomous robotic platform enhances the efficiency and speed of the quality inspection process.

Due to the high inspection surface of the wind towers, the image acquisition is performed in an open workshop with poor lighting to capture the defects with a correct illumination scheme and source. The correct design lighting system improves visual contrast, reduces environmental interference and highlights defects. Current research employs barlight model MBJ SBL-0150 LED light source, with incidence angle of 40° , due to their ease of integration, low consumption, and high lifespan.

2.2 Image processing and training dataset

Deep learning model training relies on using high-quality datasets and amounts of annotated defects to enhance the precision and dependability of Artificial Vision systems. The datasets employed in the current research cover a wide range of defects that occur during the painting process of the wind towers. Critical defect classes include pinholes, blistering, inclusions, scratches, delamination, and crumples, each of which has significant implications for the quality of the painted surface (Fig. 2). After completing the data acquisition for the wind energy use case, all images undergo annotation using squared Bounding Boxes (BBs), facilitating the identification of anomalies within the image.

Fig. 2. Painting defects on wind tower section: (a) inclusion, (b) pinhole, (c) crumple, (d) delamination and (e) scratch.

The deep learning training carried out by supervised learning techniques learns from the annotated subset to extract meaningful patterns and features that will be employed to predict class labels of unseen datasets. Current research is composed of three separate training datasets. The datasets for each training iteration are described in Table 1. The dataset acquired has been divided into three subsets terms with different weight each one, which are train (70%), test (20%) and validation (10%). The different YOLO v8 models have been trained on the train in a subset of, and the evaluated on the validation subset.

Table 1. Training dataset per iteration.

Dataset	Images	Anomalies	Inclusions	Pinhole	Scratch	Delamination	Crumple
1 st Iteration	299	342	313	11	15	2	1
2 nd Iteration	401	450	403	20	24	2	1
3 rd Iteration	443	554	441	63	47	2	1

2.3 Machine Learning

The current authors' research employs Convolution Neural Network (CNN) architecture for feature extraction and image defect detection of the painting defects. The algorithm employed in the current research is YOLO v8, which employs a deep neural network and fixed-grid regression to carry out its functions. One of the main advantages of the deep learning defect detection algorithm is that perform the feature extraction, selection, and classification of painting defects.

Table 2. Deep learning models and specifications.

Model	Layers (units)	Neurons (M)	FLOPs ¹ (B)
YOLOv8n	365	3.2	8.7
YOLOv8s	365	11.2	28.6
YOLOv8m	365	25.9	78.9
YOLOv8l	365	43.7	165.2
YOLOv8x	365	68.2	257.8

¹Number of floating point operations needed (in CPU or GPU) to run a single model inference

The performance of the YOLOv8 algorithm architecture is directly related to the selected model. For YOLOv8, there are six (6) different models that are based on the same algorithm architecture and contain the same number of convolutional layers (Table 2). However, the organization the neurons within the layers provides different performances to each model. Models with fewer neurons tend to perform better in time-constraint environments due to simple layer configuration. On the other hand, models with a vast number of neurons tend to provide significantly better mean Average Precision (mAP) results at the expense of computational resources when big datasets are employed for training purposes. Models with a higher number of neurons require a

greater number of floating point operations, which translates into higher quality hardware required to achieve real-time inspection inference.

The defect detection model is configured for the training process according to the hyperparameter settings described in Table 3. These parameters define the training process and are, among others, Learning rate initial (lr0) and final (lrf), provide information on how quickly the model updates each iteration. Epochs define the training time and represent the model passing through the dataset. It is needed for the model to converge, and too many epochs may result in overfitting models. Batch Size provides the number of images passed to the model in each epoch iteration. Image Size provides the resolution conversion to the training dataset. The YOLOv8 backbone architecture is based on a Cross Stage Partial Network (CSP-Net). During the training process, the NVIDIA GPU RTX model is used for accelerated computation.

Table 3. Deep learning training parameters.

Model hyperparameter	Description	Value
Learning rate	Affects model training time and iteration update time (lr0 and lrf)	0.01
Epochs	Number of times the model iterates through the whole dataset.	150
Batch Size	Number of images passed simultaneously to the model	[4 - 16]
Image Size	Image resolution conversion	[640 - 2088]

3 Results and discussion

Three parameters should be considered to evaluate the performance of a defect detection algorithm. The first parameter is the acquisition time, which refers to the time consumed to acquire and label the dataset needed for training, verification and testing. The second is the computational time required to train the artificial intelligence algorithm according to the parameters selected. The last parameter is the response time, which refers to the time employed from the instant that a task detection is created until the algorithm provides the detection result. The response time should be at least three times lower than the production time to avoid stoppage due to abnormal behaviour of inspection equipment. Figure 3 shows the classification results after execution the prediction model on the test dataset.

Fig. 3. Classification results of painting images after prediction model execution.

To evaluate the performance of the prediction model training by deep learning, the mean Average Precision (mAP) has been employed to evaluate the accuracy and Intersection over Union (IoU) to measure the overlap between two Bounding Boxes (BBs). The first performance metric, mAP50, determines a prediction as a truth of an IoU limit over 50%. The second performance metric is the mAP50-95, which determines a prediction as a truth of an IoU limit over 95%. At the first training scenario the deep learning algorithm was trained with YOLOv8n model employing an image resolution of 640 pixels and three different datasets (Table 1). The performance metrics used are summarized in Table 4. The results show that an increase of 212 anomalies in the third training set improved the mAP50 by 133% and the mAP50-95 by 83% concerning the first dataset trained.

Table 4. Performance metrics for scenario 1 of Deep learning training.

Iteration	Images	Anomalies	Resolution (pixels)	Model	mAP50	mAP50-95
1 st Iteration	299	342	640	YOLOv8n	0.27	0.12
2 nd Iteration	401	450	640	YOLOv8n	0.37	0.16
3 rd Iteration	443	554	640	YOLOv8n	0.63	0.22

Creating comprehensive datasets is a laborious and time-consuming process; since defective samples are naturally rare in the industrial process, the data collected should be annotated by skilled operators to identify the defects and consume a considerable amount of data for the training model phase. All these factors inhibit the further spread of deep learning algorithms for automatic industrial inspection. Machine learning training presents several strategies for dealing with small datasets, such as data augmentation, transfer learning, pre-trained models, or synthetic training data [6], [19], [20], [21]. The second training scenario trained the deep learning algorithm by modifying the YOLOv8 hyperparameters, image resolution and employing the two datasets with more labelled anomalies.

Fig. 4. Parameter accuracy based in dataset and deep learning model employed. A) 2nd interaction dataset. B) 3rd iteration dataset.

As shows in Fig. 4 the YOLOv8s employing 1080 pixels image resolution achieve better parameter-accuracy than the other configurations studied, surpassing other models that employs same image size. This improvement in accuracy has been observed in both data, and the best results improve in 107% the mAP50 and 100% the mAP50-95. Also, the increase of annotated defects in 3rd iteration has increase the accuracy the performance of YOLOv8n (Fig. 4).

An approach that can be employed to improve the precision and accuracy of the deep learning algorithm is the data augmentation method and hyperparameters model selection (Fig. 5). This data expansion methodology enables the generalization of a supplementary dataset from an initial dataset by executing a specific graphical or geometric transformation on the existing data [22]. This strategy mitigates the problem of limited training data, enhancing its robustness.

Fig. 5. Painting defect detection flow chart for model deep learning optimization.

The vision inspection system for painting defects requires high-resolution images to be processed with high accuracy, which requires a longer response time that may affect the shop floor deployment. One of the main challenges of automatic inspection based on the deep learning algorithm is the real-time performance of online quality assurance. Even though the deep learning model has been trained on-premise with the datasets, it takes a long time to train and calculate the inspection results if the task is performed Central Processing Unit (CPU) (Table 5). The computation time can affect the real-time response and execution efficiency of the automatic inspection solutions; this issue can be improved by integrating high-performance processing units to complete defect recognition such as Graphics Processing Units (GPUs).

Table 5. Time consuming for Deep learning training.

Model	Resolution (pixels)	Batch Size	CPU or GPU	Time (it/s)	Time (s/epoch)
YOLOv8n	640	16	GPU	3.84	5.73
YOLOv8n	640	16	CPU	0.17	127.38
YOLOv8x	640	4	GPU	0.32	1070.55
YOLOv8x	640	1	CPU	0.004	72432.36

The capability of autonomous machine vision systems to detect painting defects during wind tower production is crucial for quality assurance of the final product quality. In the wind energy sector, to improve manufacturing performance, the NDIT solutions must send feedback to the manufacturing process to repair, reprocess or adjust process parameters to decrease energy and materials consumption, as well as productive resources. Finally, to close the quality loop for defect detection, the information of the deep learning algorithm could be integrated with an Autonomous Guided Vehicle (AGV) and Augmented Reality Platform (ARPs). Thanks to AGV and ARP Solutions, the painting inspector can locate the defect in the real world and repair it before sending it to the next working station. The interoperability between different ZDZW solutions will increase the manufacturing resource utilization rate and quality output, decrease manufacturing costs, and improve sustainable manufacturing.

4 Conclusion

This article has summarised the research efforts to deploy an automatic vision system based on deep learning algorithms for detecting surface defects in the industrial wind tower painting process using a ZDZW strategy.

Deploying industrial vision technology can improve defect detection capabilities in early process stages, reducing material and energy consumption, equipment utilization and improving productivity. The deep learning algorithms applied to painting defect detection have led to a model that enables the identification of small defects (>40 mm²)

in huge inspection surfaces ($>500 \text{ m}^2$), which are challenging tasks to be performed manually by operators.

Regular defect data collection is crucial for model training to adapt to new defect types and ensure balanced datasets. Adding more annotated anomalies enhances the model's ability to detect and classify anomalies in various conditions, improving solution reliability and effectiveness. To effectively implement automatic computer vision inspection equipment for painting or coating defect detection, methods such as data augmentation should be employed to increase the training data set for deep learning algorithms.

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